

Computational determinacy of cellular automata

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Abstract

In literature, there have been specific one-dimensional and two-dimensional cellular automata such as Rule 110 and Conway's Game of Life that have been shown to be Turing-complete. It has been conjectured that class 4 elementary cellular automata are Turing-complete. Here, an algorithm is proposed that converts any general multi-dimensional cellular automata to an equivalent λ -expression. The achievement of this scheme is that an arrival to a "computational-cum-symbolic" representation of the solution to an partial differential equation. This is introduced as the notion of "computational determinacy". Finally, consequences such as those pertinent to formal verification of parallel systems and quantum chaos are discussed.

1 Introduction

Cellular automata (CA) are mathematical discrete structures that are defined by an array of cells, each having a state that evolves in time. They were first introduced by Stanislaw Ulam et al in the 1940s [36], but much later in the 1980s was when they were studied deeply [1, 3] in terms of their computational power, data parallelism, thermodynamics etc. Cellular automata have been a recent area of interest in research in the field of theory of computation [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 31], cryptography [2, 22, 35], traffic flow theory [4, 32, 34, 33], parallel computation [4, 5, 6] and many more. Certain classes of CA have been known to be generating pseudorandom patterns [1, 2, 3] and as a specific example, the class 4 one dimensional CA [3] have known to generate spatio-temporally local patterns that interact in complex ways and survive for a long time. With the right computational interpretation of these "patterns", rule 110 cellular automaton [11, 12, 13] and Game Of Life [14, 15] were shown to be Turing-complete and have been the only ones to be shown to be Turing-complete.

It was conjectured by Wolfram [3] that class 4 cellular automata is Turing-complete, due to those local structures interacting with each other in a "spatio-temporally" complex ways. It has been the requirement of more of a stronger

visual intuition to understand the very interpretation of Turing-completeness of CA. But in this article, the conversion works in a reverse way; here it is shown that every cellular automaton can be converted into an equivalent Turing machine, and consequently using Curry-Howard correspondence [10] and the Church-Turing thesis, an equivalent expression of the *untyped* λ calculus, via the algorithm sketched in section 3. This was informally structured by Wolfram [3], but has not been explored into its full capacity yet. One of the reasons why this is the case may be the seemingly non-trivial nature of the statement of the problem, and the plausible indirect existence of applications in many related disciplines such as computational physics or numerical analysis where solutions to 'analytically intractable' partial differential equations are solved by finite difference or mesh methods. But what I define as the "computational determinacy of cellular automata" being the very expressibility of a CA in the form of a compactified λ -expression alleviates the very problem of tractability of a given physical problem at hand. Also, the equivalent λ -expression gives insight into an expected future of the system being described, in terms of the properties it possesses.

There are other consequences such as the ease of formal verification of concurrent and parallel systems modelled using CA, Turing-equivalence and computational universality of CA, description of chaotic systems etc. discussed in section 4. But before these, the article begins with a brief overview of the mathematical formalism of cellular automata, Turing machines and λ -calculus in section 2 and then the algorithms to reduce a CA into its equivalent λ -expression have been shown and analysed in section 3. The article has been concluded in section 5.

2 Background

I would be reducing a cellular automata to a λ -expression in stages by first converting it into a Turing machine but I would do that in section 3. Let us first begin by preliminary definitions. I define an *n-dimensional r-neighbourhood first-order cellular automaton* as a 4-tuple (S, Q_t, N, f) where $S \subseteq \mathbb{F}$, \mathbb{F} is some known field, known as the set of states; Q_t is an $l_1 \times l_2 \times l_3 \cdots \times l_n$ matrix for an instance of time t , where $\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \quad \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\}$, $Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] \in S$; N is an $r \times n$ matrix known as the neighbourhood matrix; and finally $f : S^{r+1} \rightarrow S$, known as the transition function. Here the future state of a cellular automaton is defined in the following way:

$$\forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n\} \forall i_k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, l_k\},$$

$$Q_{t+1}[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n] = f(Q_t[i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n], h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_r)$$

$$\text{where } h_m = Q_t[\{(i_k + N[m, k]) \bmod l_k\} \forall k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l_m\}]$$

$$\forall m \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, r\}.$$

The matrix Q_t is usually recognised in regular literature [22, 1, 2, 3] as the *grid* of the cellular automaton. A simple example of first-order cellular automata with $n = 1, r = 2$ are the elementary cellular automata with any Wolfram rule as its transition function [22, 3] where the neighbourhood matrix $N = (1, -1)^T$ and the set of states $S = \{0, 1\}$. Essentially the notion of the neighbourhood matrix and the location of an element, the *cell* of the automaton, in the *grid* would be important to us. Mechanically or *algorithmically* describing, what one does is for every cell in the grid, one consults the neighbourhood of the cell as described in the neighbourhood matrix, takes their values and computes the transition function and updates the value in the next instance of time. The same is done *simultaneously*, and not *sequentially* or *iteratively*, for all the cells in the grid. This inherently inculcates, in this discrete structure, highly-scaling data parallelism and thus is effective in describing massively-parallel computing environments [4, 5, 6]. This invites us in definition of the general k^{th} order cellular automata. However, here, I won't be formally elaborating upon this; it's just that the transition function now takes into consideration elements of the grid in its immediate previous k instances of time, similar to the way I define a k^{th} -order partial differential equation. In fact, a partial differential equation can be expressed as a cellular automata and vice-versa [7].

A *single-tape Turing machine* M is an 8-tuple $\langle Q, \Gamma, \sqcup, \Sigma, \delta, q_0, q_{\text{accept}}, q_{\text{reject}} \rangle$ [8],

1. Q is a set of states.
2. Σ is the input alphabet not containing the blank symbol \sqcup .
3. Γ is the tape alphabet, where $\sqcup \in \Gamma$ and $\Sigma \in \Gamma$.
4. $\delta : Q \times \Gamma \rightarrow Q \times \Gamma \times \{L, R\}$ is the transition function. Here, L denotes left shift and R denotes right shift.
5. $q_0 \in Q$ is the start state.
6. $q_{\text{accept}} \in Q$ is the accept state.
7. $q_{\text{reject}} \in Q$ is the reject state, where $q_{\text{reject}} \neq q_{\text{accept}}$.

Extending the above definition, one can establish the notion of a *multi-tape Turing machine* M to be a 6-tuple $\langle Q, \Gamma, s, \sqcup, F, \delta \rangle$,

1. As before, Q is a set of states.
2. Γ is a finite set of tape symbols, which include both the input alphabets of the individual tapes, but not the blank symbol \sqcup .
3. $s \subseteq Q$ is the initial set of states.
4. $\sqcup \in \Gamma$ is the blank symbol.

5. $F \subseteq Q$ is the set of final states.
6. $\delta : Q \times \Gamma^k \rightarrow Q \times \Gamma^k \times \{L, R, S\}^k$ is the transition function. Here, L denotes left shift and R denotes right shift, and S denotes no shift.

It can be easily shown that a k -tape Turing machine could be easily reduced to a single-tape Turing machine by relabelling what a combination of k -tape symbols would mean in the "uni-tape" system, as is demonstrated in [9], a fact that I would be using later in section 3.

For this article, it would be nice and neat to use *untyped λ -calculus* where the expression has got no specific *type* as such [10]. Attaching a "type" to a λ -expression defeats the purpose of this article in a true sense; one must recollect that cellular automata can have the set of states from any field, or any "type" so to speak. λ -expressions are composed of three things: variables $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n \dots$, the abstraction symbols ' λ ' and '.', and the parentheses '()', and the set of λ -expressions, Λ , can be defined inductively,

1. If ' v ' is a variable, then $v \in \Lambda$.
2. If ' x ' is a variable and $M \in \Lambda$, then $(\lambda x.M) \in \Lambda$. In this case, x is a *bounded variable*; in any other form/usage, it is a *free variable*.
3. If $M, N \in \Lambda$, then $(MN) \in \Lambda$.

On such a universal set of all the λ -expressions, one has the following invariances on them.

1. If $E(a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \Lambda$ is a λ -expression in variables $a_k, \forall k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and a'_0 is another variable, then $E(a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = E(a'_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$. This is known as *α -conversion*.
2. For any expression b and variables p, v , $((\lambda p.b)v) = b[p := v]$. This is known as *β -reduction*.
3. For any expression f and a variable x , $((\lambda x.f)x) = f$. This is known as *η -reduction*.

As an immediate recollection of the fact that I are discussing only untyped lambda calculus, the reason for the same that of all the λ -calculi, only the untyped is known to be Turing-complete, not the simply-typed or the polymorphic [10].

As of now, the only CA known to be Turing-complete are the Conway's Game of Life and the rule 110 CA [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. And as of now, Turing-completeness has been proven just by finding patterns that help in emulation of individual features of the Turing machine such as the tape, alphabet, movement of the tape head, or sophisticated "gliding patterns" that represent boolean logical constants and functions. Such a process fails to be generalisable and scalable for most of other class-4 CA [12]. In section 3, the basic mechanism of the

evolution of the CA in terms of referral of a cell to its neighbours is employed to reduce it to a multi-tape Turing machine, and thus subsequently to a single-tape Turing machine and then to an equivalent λ -expression. The resulting λ -expression represents the cellular automata in its entirety, and thus serves as a signatory "analytical" expression of several bound variables, besides a mandatory variable of time. This one single "program" embeds/encapsulates within itself all the computational determinacy/chaos of the cellular automata.

3 Reducing a cellular automata to a λ -expression

As a first step, one would first convert a CA into a multi-tape Turing machines. Given the complexity of the procedure, I would not give any formal treatment to the process. Let us recollect how a general CA works, each cell is updated simultaneously, where it looks at its neighbours and consults the transition function to know it's value in the next instance of time. This process can be emulated in a multi-tape Turing machine, and I would be showing that using an example. Let us begin with an elementary cellular automata with n cells in the grid consisting of bits. To emulate its functionality, I would take $2n$ tapes, all with the same content as the grid of the CA. The tape heads of all the tapes would stand at different positions; precisely, corresponding to the i^{th} cell of the grid would correspond to the tape head of the $(2i - 1)^{th}$ and $(2i)^{th}$ tapes to be at the i^{th} tape. Now we would follow the algorithm 1. By "following", I really mean the actual functionality of the multi-tape Turing machine behaving like a given elementary CA.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm followed by a multi-tape Turing machine that works like a given elementary CA with a transition function f

- 1: T_p^q represents the bit in the p^{th} position of the q^{th} tape.
 - 2: **while** true **do**
 - 3: For all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ simultaneously
 - 4: Remember the bit $x_0 \leftarrow T_i^{2i-1}$ and move the tape head of the $(2i - 1)^{th}$ tape to the right.
 - 5: Remember the bit $x_1 \leftarrow T_{i+1}^{2i-1}$ and move the tape head of the $(2i - 1)^{th}$ tape to the left twice.
 - 6: Remember the bit $x_2 \leftarrow T_{i-1}^{2i-1}$ and move the tape head of the $(2i - 1)^{th}$ tape to the right.
 - 7: Now transfer the $T_i^{2i} \leftarrow f(x_0, x_1, x_2)$.
 - 8: Again for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ simultaneously
 - 9: $T_{i-1}^{2i-1} \leftarrow T_{i-1}^{2i-2}$
 - 10: $T_i^{2i-1} \leftarrow T_i^{2i}$
 - 11: $T_{i+1}^{2i-1} \leftarrow T_{i+1}^{2i+2}$
 - 12: Now set the tapes of $(2i - 1)^{th}$ tape and $(2i)^{th}$ tape to the i^{th} position again.
 - 13: **end while**
-

Now we can comfortably extend the procedure prescribed by algorithm 1 for a general n -dimensional CA with r neighbours. For this, since we need two copies of all the cells of the grid, we would need $2l_1 l_2 \cdots l_n$ tapes in the multi-tape Turing machine, using the definition of the grid of the cellular automata

Figure 1: A portion of the multi-tape Turing machine (drawn using JFLAP application) that gets copied for all the tapes that look for the neighbours and compute the transition function.

in section 2. In the case of elementary CA dealt by algorithm 1, every instance of the time requires 8 simultaneous movements of all the tape heads. In the emulation of general first-order CA, the entire grid will have to be represented into a tape of length $l_1 l_2 \cdots l_n$ and positions need to be indexed using vectorisation [16] or Morton space filling techniques [17, 18] that generalise row-major or column-major ordering. Thus, associated with each neighbourhood matrix N for a CA (S, Q_t, N, f) , the vectorisation of the grid gives the indices of its position an ordering, thus leading to a number L_I denoting the maximum span of the positions of the neighbours which when mapped onto the tapes of the Turing machine. So, the effective number of movements of all the tape heads of the Turing machine is $4L_I$, since the tapes head move back and forth to hunt for the neighbours and do it again to re-modify all of them for the next instance of time. Thus, in general, the average-case time complexity of the emulation of the multi-tape Turing machine is $O(L_I)$, which in the worst-case scales as $O(k^n)$, where $k = \max(l_1, l_2, \cdots, l_n)$. Talking of the space consumed, restricting the "infiniteness" of the tapes, we actually need $2l_1 l_2 \cdots l_n$ tapes of length $l_1 l_2 \cdots l_n$, leading to the worst-case complexity of $O(k^{2n})$. But since we need just this one "humongous" multi-tape Turing machine, the reduction is actually constant-time. Now as discussed in section 2, every multi-tape Turing machine can be emulated using a single-tape Turing machine. If we were to reduce a

0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	1	0
0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	0	1
0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	0	1
0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	0	1
0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	0	1

Figure 2: Several steps of the time evolution of rule 28 cellular automata in a grid of 5 cells.

CA to a single-tape Turing machine with that idea, we would have the same space as the multi-tape one, but with quadratically increased time [19], leading to the asymptotic emulation time complexity of $O(k^{2n})$. And finally, as implied by the Church-Turing thesis, we can always have an equivalent λ -expression, which finally boils down to a computable function that emulates the CA.

Omohundro [7] showed that a partial differential equation (PDE) can be converted into a CA and vice-versa, and with this premise, the equivalent computable function generated by the above procedure may or may not be satisfying the difference equation represented by the CA, but for sure represents the *behaviour of the CA in terms of its time evolution*. For example let us try algorithm 1 briefly for rule 28 elementary cellular automata, whose transition function is given by,

$$f(a, b, c) = \left((1 - a)b + a(1 - b)(1 - c) \right) \text{ mod } 2$$

This CA is known to generate the Jacobsthal sequence modulo 2^{l-2} , $a_n = \left(\frac{2^n - (-1)^n}{3} \right) \text{ mod } 2^{l-2}$, l being the length of the grid. Using our algorithm to convert this into multi-tape TM (Turing machine), we get certain copies of the version of the Turing machine that looks for neighbours back and forth across each tape, and one such TM is shown in figure 1. When this multi-tape TM is converted to a single-tape TM, the evolution of the CA grid as in the figure 2 is expected to get transferred on the single-tape as in the figure 3. There are chunks of this "large" tape that contain the time evolution of the CA grid, thus the functional values are generated in the single-tape Turing machine. Some such consequences and reservations are arisen in section 4.

Figure 3: An expected snapshot of the single-tape Turing machine that emulates rule 28 CA. Here 'b' is the blank symbol.

4 Nascent consequences and questions

In this section, I would first annotate a consequence that immediately followed from the existence of an algorithm 1. Then I would discuss the possibility of formal verification of parallel systems using Hoare triples, type systems, and other automated theorem provers, just the way one can do it for *sequential systems*. Next, I would question link this newly-found correspondence between Turing machines and CA to the correspondence between neural nets and CA [22]. Finally, I would comment on the possibility of determining quantum chaos in the light of Nambu-Goto strings [37] and the plausible modelling of "chaotic bosons".

4.1 "Computational" determinacy of chaotic systems

As we saw in section 3, a PDE can always be represented by a CA of equal order, and vice versa (isomorphic to the standard finite element methods). Some PDEs (not necessarily linear) such as Poisson's equation, non-linear Schrödinger equations, linear PDEs, Sine-Gordon equations etc. are known to have exact solutions, even if it be for special cases. The others are not known or expected to have closed-form solutions in any case. Owing to the transformability of PDEs to CAs, CAs to λ -expressions, and the way the expressions contain the information of the time evolution, one can always have a function, that could otherwise be known in terms of a "table" with varying arguments, compressed in the form of a "computable" one, thence being *computationally deterministic*.

4.2 Formal verification of parallel systems

The problem of formal verification of any computer program addresses the following question: "Given a set of specifications of what the program should do, will it meet them throughout the whole time of execution?" There are several solutions stated in literature:

1. **for parallel and concurrent programs:** CIVL (Concurrency Intermediate Verification Language) [20], Promela (**P**rotocol **M**eta **L**anguage) [21, 23], UPPAAL [24] etc. that work using formal model-checking tools such as Büchi automata [23], π -calculus [25], actor model [26], timed automata [24] etc.
2. **for sequential programs:** Dafny [27], Frama-C [28], Spark ADA, BLAST etc. that work using Hoare logic [27], denotational semantics [29], axiomatic semantics [30], interactive theorem proving, satisfiability modulo theories [27], type systems [10] etc.

The temporal models for the parallel/concurrent programs concern the properties of the system that change with time and they are expected to satisfy *temporal specifications*. That's why they are mathematically structured differently than those meant for the usual sequential ones. But with the proposed algorithms, one can transit from a parallel/concurrent systems to the domain of untyped λ -calculus and then do the "typing" to actually fit the domain of the specifications. With this, one can use similar formal methods to that meant for sequential systems such as Hoare triples, SMT, axiomatic semantics etc. The additional advantage that comes along is that one does not have to explore more possibilities on the fly, instead, the states keep evolving by themselves in time, as we recall from the example discussed in section 3.

4.3 Obtaining cellular automata from "computable" functions and vice-versa

As a summary, our conversion of cellular automata to a λ -expression happens in stages: first from CA we obtain an equivalent multi-tape TM, then we convert it into a single-tape TM, and finally there's an implicit λ -expression. In an attempt to develop a formal verification of deep neural networks using a slightly modified version of cellular automata [22], one comes across a different reversal of directions during the emulation of a neural network, (equivalently, a computable function). These directions are well-elucidated in the flowchart in figure 4. Now there is a natural question that if the two directions are identical in terms of the cellular automata and the function we start with in each case. Precisely, if we begin with a CA and convert it into a λ -expression, and then convert it back to CA, do we end up getting what we started? It has been proven that the right side of the flowchart in figure 4 is NP-complete and the other way being exponential in time, and there can be infinitely many recurrence relations satisfied by a computable function.

4.4 Some consequences on quantum chaos

In this section, I begin with the Nambu-Goto action [37] S_{NG} used to describe D -dimensional strings in the Minkowskian background described by coordinates $\{X^\mu\}$ parametrised by a time-like coordinate τ and a space-like coordinate σ

$$S_{NG} = -T \int d\tau d\sigma \sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})}$$

where T is the tension of the string and,

$$\gamma_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\partial X^\mu}{\partial \sigma^\alpha} \frac{\partial X^\nu}{\partial \sigma^\beta} \eta_{\mu\nu}, \alpha, \beta \in \{0, 1\}, \sigma^0 = \tau, \sigma^1 = \sigma, \mu, \nu \in \{0, 1, \dots, D-1\}$$

Taking the variation of this action, we obtain,

$$\delta S_{NG} = -\frac{T}{2} \int d\tau d\sigma \sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} \cdot \gamma^{\alpha\beta} \delta\gamma_{\alpha\beta}$$

Figure 4: The left flowchart is of the conversion of cellular automata into an equivalently emulating λ -expression. The right is of the conversion of the neural network to a representative cellular automata.

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \delta S_{NG} &= -T \int d\tau d\sigma \sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} \cdot \gamma^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\alpha \delta X^\mu \partial_\beta X_\mu \\ \implies \delta S_{NG} &= -T \int d\tau d\sigma \partial_\alpha \left(\sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} \cdot \gamma^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\beta X_\mu \right) \delta X^\mu \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain the equations of motion,

$$\partial_\alpha \left(\sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} \cdot \gamma^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\beta X_\mu \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

all of which are non-linear and extremely complicated to have a solution in a closed-form expression. Now with this at hand, one can derive the Hamiltonian density in terms of τ and σ , and quantise the theory to explore quantum chaos. Since the classical motion would, in general, be chaotic, the equivalent cellular automata can be converted into λ -expression to explain the same, and thus the "chaotic quanta" can be described in terms of that λ -expression, or as a consequence, the newly-encouraged statistics. Accordingly, the boundary conditions decide the overall statistics of these quanta, and things like thermodynamics, glass transitions, time evolution of vitrification etc. are decided. As an example, Boltzmann's transport equation in the BGK model [32],

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \frac{\vec{p}}{m} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{x}} + \vec{F} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{p}} = \nu(f_0 - f) \quad (2)$$

where $f(\vec{x}, \vec{p}, t)$ is a distribution function of the thermodynamic system not in equilibrium, \vec{x} , \vec{p} are the position and momentum conjugated to each other, ν being the molecular collision frequency, and f_0 is the local Maxwellian distribution function. Now with the Nambu-Goto action, having a solution of X^μ for equation 1, the distribution of Boltzmann's transport equation f needs to satisfy a modified version of equation 2

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\Pi^\mu}{m} \frac{\partial f}{\partial X^\mu} + \Phi^\mu \frac{\partial f}{\partial \Pi^\mu} &= \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\Pi^\mu}{m} \left(\frac{1}{\dot{X}^\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau} + \frac{1}{X'^\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right) + \Phi^\mu \left(\frac{1}{\dot{\Pi}^\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau} + \frac{1}{\Pi'^\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right) = \nu(f_0 - f) \\ \implies \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau} \left(1 + \frac{\Pi^\mu}{m \dot{X}^\mu} + \frac{\Phi^\mu}{\dot{\Pi}^\mu} \right) + \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \left(\frac{\Pi^\mu}{m X'^\mu} + \frac{\Phi^\mu}{\Pi'^\mu} \right) &= \nu(f_0 - f) \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} S_{NG} &= -T \int d\tau d\sigma \sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} = \int d\tau d\sigma L_{NG} \\ L_{NG} &= -T \sqrt{-\det(\gamma^{\alpha\beta})} \\ \Pi_\mu &= \frac{\partial L_{NG}}{\partial \dot{X}^\mu} = \frac{T(\dot{X}_\mu(X^{\nu'} X'_\nu) - X'_\mu(\dot{X}^\nu X'_\nu))}{\sqrt{(\dot{X}^\mu X'_\mu)^2 - (\dot{X}^\mu \dot{X}_\mu)(X^{\nu'} X'_\nu)}} \\ \Phi_\mu &= \frac{\partial \Pi_\mu}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \left(\frac{T(\dot{X}_\mu(X^{\nu'} X'_\nu) - X'_\mu(\dot{X}^\nu X'_\nu))}{\sqrt{(\dot{X}^\mu X'_\mu)^2 - (\dot{X}^\mu \dot{X}_\mu)(X^{\nu'} X'_\nu)}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

On top of these, a natural constraint on the distribution function $f(\tau, \sigma)$ is given by the total number of the molecules N of the thermodynamical systems,

$$N = \int d\tau d\sigma f(\tau, \sigma)$$

and another constraint is the canonical quantisation condition in the form of the commutation relation $[X^\mu, \Pi_\mu] = i\hbar$, $\mu = \sqrt{-1}$ for bosons. Here both equations 1 and 3 are both very complicated to have a solution in the closed-form. But the whole of the thermodynamic system can be described by a "computationally deterministic" theory using the proposed scheme in section 3.

5 Conclusion

This article begins with enough formal introduction to cellular automata, Turing machines and λ calculus. Then, an algorithm to convert cellular automata into a single-tape Turing machine (and consequently, λ -expression owing to Church-Turing thesis) by first converting it to a multi-tape Turing machine.

An example of the working is presented in terms of a first-order cellular automata, and precisely, an elementary cellular automata. The emulation for a general CA was found to be exponential in time and of quadratic scaling of space. Finally, some consequences are discussed in terms of the notion of computational determinacy, formal verification of parallel systems, equivalence of CAs and computable functions, and quantum chaos. There might be some more consequences such as digital physics, universal computations, both classical and quantum cryptography etc. Turing machines have been shown to be convertible to one-dimensional cellular automata [31] with 2-linear time, and this article shows how to convert any cellular automaton to a Turing machine. There's some more future work necessary towards the Turing equivalence with CAs.

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